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Moev

**Traffic analysis and application of machine
learning techniques to detect anomalous
patterns**

Changelog

VERSION	DATE	MODIFICATIONS
0.1	04/12/2018	First draft
0.2	12/11/2020	Second draft

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, cyber attacks on communications networks are one of the main problems that must be faced in the field of cybersecurity, affecting both companies and public entities. Over the last few years, a large number of investigations have addressed the detection of different types of attack. These studies cover a wide number of possibilities, from the analysis of different communication protocols for their subsequent securization, to the construction of IDSs (Intrusion Detection Systems), which allow analyzing network traffic and detecting anomalies. in real-time communications.

The objective of this document is to present a methodology and a tool capable of analyzing data derived from network communications in order to detect attacks. To carry out this analysis, machine learning techniques are used on a set of data obtained from the CICFlowMeter tool. In addition to presenting the methodology, the document includes the techniques and methods used to build the data set.

The structure that this document follows is as follows: Chapter 2 describes the Moev tool, as well as its requirements, structure, and use; Chapter 3 presents the data set used and its construction process is detailed; Next, Chapter 4 describes the methodology and techniques for working with the data set; finally, Chapter 5 details how the tool has been validated.

MOEV TOOL

This chapter introduces the Moev tool. The following subsections describe the Moev, as well as its development and design process.

Description of Moev

When facing the task of detecting malicious traffic, it is important to use tools prepared to handle a high volume of data.

To do this, it is proposed to build a tool that allows working with large data sets related to network traffic (in the case of this project, it will be used for traffic generated by port scanning). The objective of the tool is to be able to carry out both treatment, cleaning and data processing tasks; how to apply machine learning algorithms. In this way, the program presented in this chapter will allow the agile and simple application of multiple machine learning techniques with the aim of facilitating the data analysis process.

Some of the functionalities provided by the developed tool are: data cleaning, normalization, dimensionality reduction and hyperparameterization (through the GridSearchCV method). It also offers the possibility of applying up to nine machine learning algorithms and obtaining a report with the results of said application.

The tool has been designed to work both with data sets in the **NetFlow** format, and with data sets generated by the **CICFlowMeter** tool. However, the realization of this work has been based on the CICFlow format, due to the saving of time that this tool supposes for the process of extracting the characteristics of the *pcap* files. This *software* allows you to analyze network traffic packets and extract a large number of characteristics to build a set of data (in csv format) that can be taken as input by our application. In the section ref Sub: Tools used the software **CICFlowMeter** will be described in greater depth as well as the rest of the tools used for the development of the project.

It should be noted that in the latest update of the tool, support for the treatment of images in npy format has been added.

Development process

This section details the development process carried out for the construction of the Moev tool. The following subsections expose the software requirements required by it. In the same way, the different scripts that make up the application are shown, as well as the tools used for development.

Software requirements

For the correct functioning of the developed application, the following *software* components are required in the corresponding system:

- Operating system: **Ubuntu** or other **Linux** distribution.
- **Python 2.7**
- **Pandas**: library for data analysis and manipulation.
- **Numpy**: extension of **Python**, which adds greater support for vectors and matrices as well as offering an extensive library of mathematical functions.
- **Scikit-Learn**: library aimed at machine learning in **Python**.

- **Matplotlib**: library for generating graphs in **Python**.
- **yaml**: YAML is a data serialization format.
- **Joblib**: library to improve performance and reproducibility. It allows the persistence of objects with a large amount of data.

It is necessary to take into account that the formats accepted by the tool are, as previously indicated, **CICFlowMeter**, **NetFlow** and **numpy**, therefore it is recommended to have the necessary software to obtain the sets of data in the correct format.

Source code

In this section, the source code of the tool developed during the project will be discussed. To do this, the programming languages chosen for the development of the application are briefly described and the classes or *scripts* that make up the tool are explained in detail.

For the development of the tool, the language **Python** (version *Python 2.7*) has been used mainly. **Python** is an interpreted programming language, that is, the code is translated into machine language by the interpreter as the code is executed. In other words, in interpreted languages, the compilation process is carried out, common in languages such as **C++** or **Java**.

Python is a powerful language that is widely used in robotics, data analysis, and cybersecurity. One of the most remarkable features of **Python** is that it is a *multiparadigm* language. This concept is that the language in question can support both object-oriented programming and imperative programming. In addition to the diversity of programming paradigms that **Python** supports, we must add the fact that it is a dynamic typing language, that is, a variable can take values of different types. The versatility of **Python** makes it a very useful language for projects susceptible to change. In addition, the fact of being a language that has reached such expansion among the development community has led to the existence of a great variety of libraries: from implementation of complex mathematical functions to functionalities for handling large volumes of data.

On the other hand, the use of **YAML** has been used for certain aspects of the tool. First of all, it is important to briefly describe this language. **YAML** is a data markup or serialization language. It is a language that allows data to be serialized in combinations of lists, maps, and scalar data. The goal of the language is to present a simple and readable syntax for working with the data. In the case of the tool presented in this work, **YAML**, it has been used to build the configuration file that will direct the functions developed by the tool during its execution. It has also been used to build the dictionary required by the *GridSearchCV* function, which is found in the aforementioned configuration file.

The structure of the tool consists of six main files:

- **start.py**
- **MoEv.py**
- **Cleaner.py**
- **FeatureReductor.py**
- **Preprocess.py**
- **conf.yaml**

The classes mentioned above are detailed below.

Start file

The file (**start.py**) is used to start the execution of the tool. This script should call the constructor of the **MoEv.py** class and provide it with the path of the configuration file. When executing the script, you must provide the data format (-t) with which you want to work (*CICFlowMeter*, *Netflow* or *npv*). From this script the functions available in the script **MoEv.py** are called.

Data cleaning

The **Cleaner.py** class aims to prepare the data of the *dataset* on which you want to work. For this, it presents two types of functions: functions aimed at cleaning the data and functions aimed at analyzing the data set. This class does not receive input parameters.

The functions used to clean the data are described below.

- **date_to_posix (value)**: converts the given value (in date format) to *POSIX* format (number of seconds elapsed since midnight *UTC* on January 1, 1970).
- **ip_to_integer (ip)**: converts a value in *IP*: $X1.X2.X3.X4$ format to an integer. The calculation it performs is the following:

$$newIP = X1 \text{ times } 256^3 + X2 \text{ times } 256^2 + X3 \text{ times } 256^1 + X4 \text{ times } 256^0 \quad (.1)$$

- **parse_time (df, target)**: traverse the target column converting all dates to an integer. The operation is carried out through calls to the **date_to_posix (value)** function.
- **maps_ips (df, target)**: traverse the target column converting all IP addresses to an integer. The operation is carried out through calls to the **ip_to_integer (value)** function.
- **fix_CIC_error (df)** - Finds the rows that have less than 82 values and removes them. This is done because the **CICFlowMeter** tool causes an error, on some occasions, when generating the csv file of the data, thus causing some rows to move and therefore both present incorrect readings.
- **clean_bad_columns (df)**: remove the *textit Flow ID*, *Flow Byts/s* and *Flow Pkts/s* columns. These last two columns are dropped because they sometimes cause an error as a result of their values being too large and therefore do not allow the application of machine learning algorithms. It should be noted that this function and the one previously mentioned have the requirement to work on a data set with the format of **CICFlowMeter**.
- **removeFeatures (df, list)**: removes the columns corresponding to the feature names provided through the configuration file.
- **deduplicatedRows (df)**: detect and remove duplicate rows, keeping only the first occurrence.
- **searchInfinities (df, list)**: detects the infinite values in each of the columns of the data set and replaces the value with the mean of the values in the corresponding column. The *list* parameter corresponds to a list of column names that the function will ignore. This way you can avoid working on characteristics with values in *String* format, such as the column reserved for labeling.

When cleaning the data, it is convenient to know certain characteristics of all of them, so that the user can make certain decisions regarding the treatment of problematic data. The functions whose objective is to analyze the data are described below.

- **search_NaN (df)**: goes through all the columns of the *dataset* and shows the number of NaN values in each column on the screen.

- **search_Negative (df):** go through all the columns of the *dataset* and print the number of negative values in each column.
- **search_unimportant (df):** it goes through all the columns of the *dataset* and prints those columns whose data is the same, that is, the columns that do not present a variation in their data.

Feature reduction

This class (file **FeatureReducer.py**) does not receive input parameters. Although there are multiple ways to reduce the characteristics of a data set; In this first version of the tool, only the **selectKbest (function, value, X, y)** method has been implemented, with the `textit` function parameter being the function that we want to use for the estimation (*f_regression* or *chi2*).

Preprocessing

This file (**Preprocessor.py**) contains the class in charge of preprocessing the data. The *Preprocessor* class proposes methods to rescale the data from the original data set. The methods implemented for this class are:

- **adapt_dataset (df):** removes the column corresponding to the *target* characteristic, that is, the *Label* column.
- **normalize (df):** apply a normalization algorithm on the data.
- **standardScaler (df):** apply a standardization algorithm on the data.
- **variance (df, limit, list):** calculates the variance of the different columns and eliminates those that are equal to the value provided with *limit*. Avoid columns whose names are in the *list* parameter.

Main class

The file **MoEv.py** constitutes the main class of the tool, which controls and manages the operations that can be performed. When the startup script, discussed previously, is launched, an object of class *MoEv* is created that contains the following attributes:

- **df:** object *dataframe* that contains the loaded dataset.
- **conf_file:** file type object that corresponds to the configuration file in *YAML* format.
- **cleaner:** instance of class `textbf Cleaner`.
- **input_path:** source path of the file, in *csv* format, which contains the data that the tool will work with.
- **output_path:** destination path used to export the data generated by the tool.
- **data_type:** indicates the format of the dataset with which it will work (*Netflow* or *CICFlow*).

To construct an object of the *MoEv* class, the following attributes must be supplied as parameters to the constructor:

- **file:** path of the *YML* configuration file that the tool should read.
- **size:** size with which you want to divide the *dataset*. This parameter is used to obtain the value of the variables *X_train*, *y_train*, *X_test* and *y_test*. To calculate these values, the *train_test_split()* method is used.

- **seed:** seed to randomize the selection of the subsets of the *dataset*. This parameter is used to obtain the value of the variables X_{train} , y_{train} , X_{test} and y_{test} . To calculate these values, the *train_test_split()* method is used.
- **target:** name of the column that corresponds to the target variable (y), that is, the name of the characteristic to be predicted.

To finish with the components of this class we will talk about its methods. In addition to the *Get* and *Set* methods, which allow obtaining or modifying the class attributes, *MoEv*, it has the following methods or functions:

- **to_csv():** exports the content of the *df* attribute to the path indicated in the *output_path* attribute.
- **update_X_y(target):** sets the value of the X and y attributes to new values calculated based on the target variable provided as input. If the attributes X and y have not been previously created, create them.
- **splitDF(size, seed):** randomly generates subsets from the *dataset*, with which you are working, to obtain the values of the variables X_{train} , y_{train} , X_{test} and y_{test} .
- **cleanDataset():** calls the corresponding methods of the **Cleaner** class that have been specified in the configuration file to obtain a clean *dataframe* object.
- **analyzeDataset():** calls the corresponding methods of the **Cleaner** class that have been indicated in the configuration file. This method displays information related to the data in the *dataset* columns in order to detect problems through manual review.
- **preprocessDataset():** calls the corresponding methods of the **Preprocessor** class that have been indicated in the configuration file. Generate a *dataframe* object with the rescaled data.
- **reductFeatures():** calls the corresponding methods of the **FeatureReductor** class that have been indicated in the configuration file. Generates a *dataframe* object whose number of characteristics has been reduced.
- **createModels():** create the machine learning models indicated in the configuration file. If specified in the **conf.yaml** file, the created models are stored in the specified folder. After the models are created, a call is made to **testModels (model)** to test them. It is important to say that the user can indicate through the configuration file that new models are not created but rather that the models stored in a specific folder are used. In this way the models will be loaded and tested with the **testModels (model)** method.
- **testModels (model):** receives a model and calculates the metrics that have been indicated in the configuration file.

Configuration file

This file (**conf.yaml**) contains the configuration of the tool that will determine which functions will be executed once the startup *script* is launched. First, it is necessary to indicate the paths that will be used when loading (*input_path*) and exporting (*output_path*) the corresponding data set. It is also necessary to indicate the folder where the trained models are saved, which must be created. Inside the folder where we save the models, we must also create a folder whose name is the type of data to be used. The rest of the file consists of the functions that each of the classes implemented in the tool can perform. The configuration values are *True* or *False*, in this way the user can indicate in a simple

way if he wants a certain function to be executed or not. Below is a portion of the code in the file for the purpose of illustrating this explanation.

```
numpy:
  data_raw: "./images/npv_total_raw_train.npy"
  data_label: "./images/npv_total_label_train.npy"
flows:
  input_path: "./flows/data_train.csv"
  output_path: ""

models_path: "./models/"

#Data prepare
cleanData:
  enabled: True
  fixCICError: False
  removeBadColumns: False
  parseIP: True
  parseDate: False
  removeFeature:
    enabled: False
    list: ['Flow ID', 'Src IP', 'Dst IP', 'Timestamp', 'Fwd Header Length1'
          ↪ ]
  removeDuplicatedRows: False
  export: False
#Data analysis
analyzeData:
  enabled: True
  nanValues: True
  negativeValues: True
  unimportantCol: True
  infiniteValues:
    enabled: False
    list: ['Label']
  export: False
#Preprocessing
preprocess:
  enabled: True
  variance:
    enabled: False
    limit: 0
    list: ['Label']
  function: standardScaler #normalize | standardScaler | none
  saveDf: False
  export: False
#Feature extraction
featureReduction:
  enabled: False
```

```
kbest:  
  enabled: False  
  function: f_regression #f_regression | chi2  
  k: 2  
export: False
```

```
Metrics:  
  accuracy: True  
  confusionMatrix: True  
  overfitting: False  
  report: True
```

Finally, there is the file **Model.py**, from which the machine learning models implemented by the tool inherit. The objective of the proposed structure is for the tool to be scalable, so that any user can incorporate their own model into the tool. This file defines the functions that the other models that inherit from this class must implement. The **Model** class has two attributes that store information about the model itself: *classifier* and *modelName*. In addition to the *Get* and *Set* methods of the aforementioned attributes, the class defines the following methods:

- **fit (X_train, y_train):** apply the *fit (X_train, y_train)* method and generate a classifier.
- **predict (X_test):** generate predictions for the model's classifier.
- **accuracy_score (and_test, predictions):** generates the metrics obtained from the model predictions obtained through the previous method.
- **classification_report (predictions, Y_test):** shows the model report.
- **confusion_Matrix (df):** show the confusion matrix
- **gridsearch (X, y, parameters):** apply the *GridSearchCV* method to locate hyperparameters that provide optimal results. To do this, it requires that a dictionary be provided as input with the parameters that the model can take. This dictionary (key-value format) is found in the configuration file.

Design

This section shows the diagrams generated in the design phase. A total of three diagrams have been made: use case diagram, class diagram, and component diagram.

The use case diagram 1 and the class diagram 2 are closely linked to the product stack, since the different functionalities have been extracted from these diagrams that, subsequently have been translated into user stories.

On the other hand, the component diagram 3 shows the interaction between the libraries used by the application and its classes.

Figure 1: Use case diagram.

Figure 2: Class diagram.

Figure 3: Component diagram.

DATASET

This chapter will describe the built dataset as well as the construction process for it. A comparison is also made with the NetFlow fields in order to evaluate the possibility of generalizing the methodology in the near future.

CICFlowMeter

CICFlowMeter or **ISCXFlowMeter** is a software focused on the analysis of network traffic flows. The tool has been developed and distributed by "Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity" (**CIC**). The tool allows you to analyze sets of files in *pcap* format and generate bidirectional streams (*Biflow*), based on them. The tool allows you to extract up to 84 characteristics from the analyzed files and thus generate a file (.csv format). The type of the extracted characteristics can be from time formats to binary data relative to the communication *flags*. It is important to mention that, in the 84 characteristics extracted by CICFlowMeter, the following 6 are included, which are identifiers of the flow itself:

- **FlowID:** is the flow identifier. It has the following format: *SourceIp-DestinationIp-SourcePort-DestinationPort-Protocol*
- **SourceIP:** source IP address.
- **DestinationIP:** destination IP address.
- **SourcePort:** port of origin.
- **DestinationPort:** port of destination.
- **Protocol:** numerical value of the communication protocol used.

It is important to mention that the tool allows working in two modes: *online* and *offline*. In this way, the tool allows extracting, in real time, the characteristics of the packets obtained from the device's network interface (*online* mode); Or, analyze *pcaps* files extracted from a communication that has already taken place (*offline* mode). For the development of the tool, we have worked in *offline* mode, since data generated through traffic simulations has been used.

Dataset fields

The data being worked on is generated with the CICFlowMeter tool. Therefore, the dataset format used depends on the characteristics that the tool extracts from the captured packets. That is, the dataset first has 84 features per network flow.

The characteristics extracted by the CICFlowMeter tool range from a series of *flags* relative to each flow, to data related to the size of the packets, number of bytes or data, and time measurements.

The table 1 lists the flags considered by the tool. The table 2 shows all the characteristics extracted by CICFlowMeter, which correspond to the fields of the constructed dataset.

Table 1: Flags considered by CICFlowMeter.

Flag	Meaning
PSH	Push. Allows synchronization between the transport layer and the application layer
URG	Urgent. Prioritize sending the data
FIN	Finish. Used to end communication
SYN	Synchronization. First step of the textit three-way-handsake process. Start of communication
RST	Reset. Used to end the connection
ACK	Acknowledgment. Recognition of packages sent successfully
CWR	Congestion Window Reduced. Indicates that it has received a packet labeled with the ECE flag
ECE	Indicates if the TCP pair supports textit Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN)

Dataset construction

Once we know the characteristics that CICFlowMeter extracts, we can build a set of data on which to start working. CICFlowMeter does not generate an output that we can use as a dataset immediately. The output provided by the tool consists, depending on the parameters provided, in a set of CSV files, which contain a certain number of streams with their corresponding characteristics. The first step, therefore, is to build a data set that contains all the data generated by CICFlowMeter and distributed in different files. For this we have made a script in **Python** (making use of the **pandas python** library) that allows us, given a directory containing several files with csv format, to generate a *dataframe* whose content consists in the merge of the files.

The generated file does not contain the streams in order. This result is due to the way the script traverses the input files directory. The flows contain a time stamp field, so the fact that the flows are not ordered will not affect the work process but simply the display of the dataset.

At this point, we have a dataframe that contains all the data generated by CICFlowMeter. The next step is to prepare and clean the dataset, one of the most important steps in ensuring classifier accuracy. We'll go deeper into preparing the dataset in the section.

It is necessary to indicate that to carry out the first tests we have worked on two datasets. The first of them has been obtained from a simulation of attacks on the honeypot located in the laboratory. The attacks, carried out on October 15, 2019, were of the DoS type and were carried out using the HULK and LOIC tools.

On the other hand, the second dataset was created during November 27 and 28, 2019, with the aim of having a greater amount of data, as well as working on data that present greater variation.

Create the dataset

Building a traffic dataset that performs well is difficult. The dataset developed and that will be described in this section was carried out in a period of two days and with the aim of being able to start making tests and comparisons between data in a short period of time.

When building the dataset, the problem of mixing normal traffic with anomalous traffic was raised. To solve this problem, it was decided to capture traffic in isolation. On the 27th and 28th, the necessary

traffic was generated to compose the dataset. The types of attacks chosen for generating the anomalous traffic were the following:

- DoS using the HULK tool
- DoS using the Overload tool
- Port scanning using the Nmap tool
- Port scanning using the Netcat tool
- Brute force attack using the Hydra tool

Once the attacks were launched and the traffic captured (*pcaps*), the CICFlowMeter tool was used to extract the characteristics of the flows and generate the corresponding csv. The final result was the obtaining of 5 spreadsheets (one for each one of the attacks carried out), which have the characteristics that are reflected in the table 3.

Table 3: Characteristics of the attack simulation files.

Attack	CSV size(KB)	No. csv records	Date
DoS Hulk	14.060	20643	27/11/2019
DoS Overload	69.063	173282	27/11/2019
Nmap port scan	22.786	65554	28/11/2019
Netcat port scan	22.759	65347	28/11/2019
Brute Force Hydra	41.247	80009	27/11/2019

After carrying out the attacks, normal traffic began to be captured. To generate normal traffic, a small script was developed that launched different requests in a loop on a simulated robot. Through CICFlowMeter, repeating the process performed with bad traffic, the csv corresponding to normal traffic was generated. The size of the obtained file is 23,080KB and contains 47923 records.

Before working with the datasets obtained, they underwent a labeling and cleaning process, a process in which we will delve further in the next chapter.

To obtain the final dataset, a small script was implemented that allows joining the 5 files in a single csv.

NetFlow fields

In this section the different NetFlow fields are shown through the table 4, we can see a total of 79 fields. These fields correspond to the definitions of the different fields that a NetFlow export tool can support. The data presented in this section correspond to the fields of the packet headers as well as its properties and have been obtained through the NetFlow documentation available in RFC 3954 ²

²RFC 3954 available at: <https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc3954.txt>

Table 2: CICFlowMeter fields.

Field Name	Description
Flow ID	Flow identifier. The identifier has the following form: SourceIp-DestinationIp-SourcePort-DestinationPort-Protocol
Src IP	Source IP address
Src Port	Source port
Dst IP	Destination IP address
Dst Port	Destination port
Protocol	Communication protocol. According to the protocol identifier number ¹
Timestamp	Date the flow started. Format: <i>dd / mm / yyyy hh: mm: ss AM / PM</i>
Flow duration	Flow duration in microseconds
total Fwd Packet	total packets in direction <i>forward</i>
total Bwd Packet	total packets in direction <i>backward</i>
total Length of Fwd Packet	total packet size in direction <i>forward</i>
total Length of Bwd Packet	total packet size in direction <i>backward</i>
Fwd Packet Length Min	Minimum packet size in direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd Packet Length Max	Maximum packet size in direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd Packet Length Mean	Average of the packet size in direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd Packet Length Std	Standard deviation of packet size in direction <i>forward</i>
Bwd Packet Length Min	Minimum packet size in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd Packet Length Max	Maximum packet size in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd Packet Length Mean	Average of the packet size in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd Packet Length Std	Standard deviation of packet size in direction <i>backward</i>
Flow Byte / s	Number of flow bytes per second
Flow Packets / s	Number of flow packets per second
Flow IAT Mean	Average time between two packets sent in the same flow
Flow IAT Std	Standard deviation of the time between two packets sent in the same flow
Flow IAT Max	Maximum time between two packets sent in the same flow
Flow IAT Min	Minimum time between two packets sent in the same flow
Fwd IAT Min	Minimum time between two packets sent in direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd IAT Max	Maximum time between two packets sent in direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd IAT Mean	Mean of the time between two packets sent in the direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd IAT Std	Standard deviation of time between two packets sent in direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd IAT Total	Total time between two packets sent in direction <i>forward</i>
Bwd IAT Min	Minimum time between two packets sent in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd IAT Max	Maximum time between two packets sent in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd IAT Mean	Mean of the time between two packets sent in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd IAT Std	Standard deviation of time between two packets sent in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd IAT Total	Total time between two packets sent in direction <i>backward</i>
Fwd PSH flag	Number of times the <i>flag</i> PSH has been sent in packets traveling in the direction <i>forward</i> (0 in UDP).
Bwd PSH flag	Number of times the <i>flag</i> PSH has been sent in packets traveling in the <i>backward</i> direction (0 in UDP).
Fwd URG flag	Number of times the <i>flag</i> URG has been sent in packets traveling in the direction <i>forward</i> (0 in UDP).
Bwd URG flag	Number of times the <i>flag</i> URG has been sent in packets traveling in the <i>backward</i> direction (0 in UDP).
Fwd Header Length	Total bytes used by <i>headers</i> in direction <i>forward</i>
Bwd Header Length	Total bytes used by <i>headers</i> in direction <i>backward</i>
FWD Packets / s	Number of packets <i>forward</i> per second
BWD Packets / s	Number of packets <i>backward</i> per second
Min Packet Length	Minimum length of a packet
Max Packet Length	Maximum length of a packet
Packet Length Mean	Average length of a packet
Packet Length Std	Standard deviation of the length of a packet
Packet Length Variance	Variance of the length of a packet
FIN Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>FIN</i>
SYN Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>SYN</i>
RST Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>RST</i>
PSH Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>PSH</i>
ACK Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>ACK</i>
URG Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>URG</i>
CWR Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>CWR</i>
ECE Flag Count	Number of packets with <i>ECE</i>
down / Up Ratio	Down / Up Ratio
Average Packet Siz	Average Packet Size
Avg Fwd Segment Size	Average size observed in direction <i>forward</i>
Avg Bwd Segment Size	Average size observed in direction <i>backward</i>
Fwd Header Length	Length of the header of the sent packet
Fwd Avg Bytes / Bulk	Average Bulk Rate Bytes at address <i>forward</i>
Fwd Avg Packet / Bulk	Average of bulk rate packets in direction <i>forward</i>
Fwd AVG Bulk Rate	Average Bulk Rate in <i>forward</i>
direction Bwd Avg Bytes / Bulk	Average Bulk Rate Bytes at address <i>backward</i>
Bwd Avg Packet / Bulk	Average of bulk rate packets in direction <i>backward</i>
Bwd AVG Bulk Rate	Average Bulk Rate in <i>backward</i>
direction Subflow Fwd Packets	Average number of packets in a subflow towards <i>forward</i>
Subflow Fwd Bytes	Average number of bytes in a subflow in direction <i>forward</i>
Subflow Bwd Packets	Average number of packets in a subflow towards <i>backward</i>
Subflow Bwd Bytes	Average number of bytes in a subflow in direction <i>backward</i>
Init _Win _bytes _forward	Total number of bytes sent in the initial window at address <i>forward</i>
Init _Win _bytes _backward	Total number of bytes sent in the initial window at address <i>backward</i>
Act _data _pkt _forward	Number of packets with at least 1 byte of the TCP <i>payload</i> at the address <i>forward</i>
min _sec _size _forward	Minimum observed segment size in direction <i>forward</i>
Active Min	Minimum time a flow was active before being <i>idle</i>
Active Mean	Average time a stream was active before being <i>idle</i>
Activate Max	Maximum time a stream was active before being <i>idle</i>
Active Std	Standard deviation of the time a stream was active before being <i>idle</i>
Idle Min	Minimum time a flow was <i>idle</i> before being active
Idle Mean	Average time a flow was <i>idle</i> before being active
Idle Max	Maximum time a flow was <i>idle</i> before being active
Idle Std	Standard deviation of the time a flow was <i>idle</i> before being active
Label	Feature reserved to label data

Table 4: NetFlow fields.

Field Name	Description
IN_BYTES	N x 8 bit length counter of the number of bytes associated with an IP stream. By default N is 4.
IN_PKTS	N x 8 bit length counter of the number of packets associated with an IP stream. By default N is 4.
FLows	Number of flows that have been added.
PROTOCOL	IP Protocol
TOS	Byte of service type, configured when entering the incoming interface
TCP_FLAGS	Accumulation of all TCP flags that appear in the flow
L4_SRC_PORT	source TCP / UDP port number
IPv4_SRC_ADDR	Source IPv4 address
SRC_MASK	Number of contiguous bits in source subnet mask
INPUT_SNMP	Index of the input interface
L4_DST_PORT	destination TCP / UDP port number
IPv4_DST_ADDR	Destination IPv4 address
DST_MASK	Number of contiguous bits in destination subnet mask
OUTPUT_SNMP	Index of the output interface
IPv4_NEXT_HOP	IPv4 next hop address (hop router)
SRC_AS	Source BGP (Border Gateway Protocol) autonomous system number
DST_AS	Destination BGP autonomous system number
BGP_IPv4_NEXT_HOP	Next hop of router IP address in BGP domain
MUL_DST_PKTS	Outgoing packet counter (IP multicast) with size N x 8 bits for packets associated with the IP stream
MUL_DST_BYTES	Outbound Byte Counter (IP multicast) with size N x 8 bits for packets associated with the IP stream
LAST_SWITCHED	sysUptime in milliseconds that the last packet in the stream was <i>switched</i>
FIRST_SWITCHED	sysUptime in milliseconds the first packet in the stream was <i>switched</i>
OUT_BYTES	Outgoing counter with size N x 8 bits for the number of bytes associated with an IP stream
OUT_PKTS	Outgoing counter with size N x 8 bits for the number of packets associated with an IP stream
IPv6_SRC_ADDR	Source IPv6 address
IPv6_DST_ADDR	Destination IPv6 address
IPv6_SRC_MASK	Size of source IPv6 mask in contiguous bits
IPv6_DST_MASK	Size of destination IPv6 mask in contiguous bits
IPv6_FLOW_LABEL	IPv6 Flow Label (RFC 2460)
ICMP_TYPE	type of ICMP (Internet Control Message Protocol) packet. ICMP Type x 256 + ICMP code
MUL_IGMP_TYPE	Internet Group Management Protocol (IGMP) packet type
SAMPLING_INTERVAL	When using sampled NetFlow, it is the rate ("rate") at which packets are sampled
SAMPLING_ALGORITHM	for sampled NetFlow (<i>platform wide</i>): 0 x 01 deterministic sampling , 0 x 02 random sampling . Used in conjunction with SAMPLING_INTERVAL
FLOW_ACTIVE_TIMEOUT	Time value (in seconds) for active flow entries in the NetFlow cache
FLOW_INACTIVE_TIMEOUT	Time value (in seconds) for inactive flow entries in the NetFlow cache
ENGINE_TYPE	Type of flow " <i>switching engine</i> " (route processor, linecard ...)
ENGINE_ID	ID number of the " <i>switching engine</i> " of the flow
TOTAL_BYTES_EXP	N x 8-bit size counter of the number of bytes exported by the observation domain (<i>Observation Domain</i>)
TOTAL_PKTS_EXP	N x 8 bit size counter of the number of packets exported by the observation domain (<i>Observation Domain</i>)
TOTAL_FLOWS_EXP	Counter of size N x 8 bits of the number of flows exported by the observation domain (<i>Observation Domain</i>)
MPLS_TOP_LABEL_TYPE	Label (TOP) of type Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS)
MPLS_TOP_LABEL_IP_ADDR	"Forwarding Equivalent Class" corresponding to the Top Label of MPLS
FLOW_SAMPLER_ID	Identifier shown in " <i>show flow-sampler</i> "
FLOW_SAMPLER_MODE	The type of the algorithm used for data sampling
FLOW_SAMPLER_RANDOM_INTERVAL	Packet interval at which to sample
DST_TOS	Service Type Byte, configured on exit on outgoing interface
SRC_MAC	Source MAC address
DST_MAC	Destination MAC address
SRC_VLAN	Virtual LAN identifier associated with the ingress interface
DST_VLAN	Virtual LAN identifier associated with the egress interface
IP_PROTOCOL_VERSION	Version of the Internet Protocol (IP). Set to 4, for IPv4, and 6 for IPv6. By default the value 4
DIRECTION	Direction of flow: 0 for incoming flow (ingress) and 1 for outgoing flow (egress)
BGP_IPv6_NEXT_HOP	IPv6 address of the next hop router (next-hop router)
IPv6_OPTION_HEADERS	Encoded field (bit-encoded) that identifies the <i>headers</i> of IPv6 options found in the stream
MPLS_LABEL_1	MPLS label in stack position 1
MPLS_LABEL_2	MPLS label in stack position 2
MPLS_LABEL_3	MPLS label in stack position 3
MPLS_LABEL_4	MPLS label in stack position 4
MPLS_LABEL_5	MPLS label in stack position 5
MPLS_LABEL_6	MPLS label in stack position 6
MPLS_LABEL_7	MPLS label in stack position 7
MPLS_LABEL_8	MPLS label in stack position 8
MPLS_LABEL_9	MPLS label in stack position 9
MPLS_LABEL_10	MPLS label at stack position 10

MACHINE LEARNING PROCESS

This chapter describes the different stages that have been carried out in order, through machine learning techniques, to achieve a model that allows us to detect anomalies in network traffic.

The first step we must take is to decide which machine learning technique we are going to use. In our case we want to train a model from data that we ourselves have generated and therefore control; to later work with data that we do not know. In this work context, the technique that best fits is supervised learning. For this we need a set of training data, that is, data of which we know its classification. We will call this data known as **tagged data**. We will see in more detail the data labeling process in the corresponding section .

Data preparation

Preparing your data is an essential part of working with machine learning and data mining. It is important that we make a distinction between preparing the data and pre-processing the data, which we will talk about in the section .

In this section we will focus on the phase that we have called data preparation. This phase consists of cleaning the data, eliminating possible errors, and adapting said data so that they can be processed by the algorithms that will subsequently be applied to them.

We can organize the data preparation process in the following phases:

- Data labeling
- Dataset analysis
- Cleaning the dataset
- Data transformation

The data preparation phase is essential due to the impact that the treatment carried out on the data can have on the final results. Transforming data or managing errors in a specific way can cause very large variations in the results obtained. There are a large number of lines of research dedicated to studying the effects of preparing the data in one way or another on the final models.

Data labeling

As we have previously commented, we will use the supervised learning technique. This technique requires working with labeled data sets with which to train the models. In our case we are working with data from communication networks and therefore we must generate traffic in a controlled way.

In a first approach we have worked with a dataset built from data extracted from a DOS attack simulation on our honeypot (5). In this case we will distinguish between normal traffic and anomalous or attack traffic. We will label the data in the following way:

- Normal traffic labeled 0
- Abnormal traffic labeled 1

The labeling process has been carried out through the use of a **Python** script that takes as input values identifying each flow and assigns them the indicated label. When generating the attack traffic, a footprint of each flow was stored. The information we have to carry out the labeling is the following:

- Source IP
- Destination IP
- Destination Port
- Protocol
- Start time
- End time
- Date the attack was performed

Table 5: Information attack on October 15, 2019

Ataque	Puerto	IP Origen	IP Destino	Hora de inicio	Hora de fin
Hulk No Server	80	185.179.104.131	193.146.101.173	13:27:00	13:32:00
Hulk Fake Server	80	185.179.104.131	193.146.101.173	13:37:00	13:42:00
Hulk Docker	6901	185.179.104.131	193.146.101.173	13:46:00	13:52:00
Hulk Docker	6901	185.179.104.1	193.146.101.173	13:46:00	13:52:00

In the dataset corresponding to the attack simulation carried out on October 15, 2019 (whose information we can see in the table 5) on the laboratory honeypot, 387 026 flows out of a total of 491 512 were labeled as anomalous traffic flows contained in the dataset. Procently, this data reflects that approximately 78.7% of the data in the dataset was labeled as anomalous traffic.

The labeling process on the dataset generated on November 28 and 27 and containing traffic from a greater variety of attacks was simpler than in the case described above, since the traffic capture has been carried out in isolation, therefore all the traffic of each of the datasets obtained during the attack was labeled 1 while the data obtained from the normal traffic generation was labeled 0.

It is necessary to note that the tests prior to this document have been carried out on the previous dataset. The ideal scenario is to work with a larger dataset with a more equal distribution between anomalous traffic and normal traffic. In order to build a dataset with these characteristics, it is necessary to generate and capture traffic of both types in a controlled environment.

Dataset analysis

Before starting to clean, transform or apply preprocessing algorithms, it is necessary to carry out a preliminary analysis of the data to know the behavior of the same and detect possible errors or irrelevant information.

The data that can cause errors are those that have NaN values, empty or negative. It is important to locate these types of data and their quantity, since the way to deal with these problematic values can

vary from column to column.

To solve this problem we have implemented a **python** script that analyzes the dataset by going through its columns and obtains certain information regarding the values that we have mentioned previously. The information that we can obtain by executing this script is:

- Columns containing NaN values and how many NaN values they have.
- Columns containing negative values and how many negative values they have.
- Columns that contain all the same values, that is, their data does not vary.

Through this analysis we can obtain useful information when cleaning the data (we will see the data cleaning in the section). However, we can also perform another type of analysis to detect other errors, such as, for example, counting the number of data in each row to see if there are empty values.

In our case, we found an error introduced by CICFlowMeter (probably during the moment of exporting the data to the csv format). This error causes some values to be shifted to the left, that is, the dataset presents rows with values that do not correspond to the correct column or has empty cells. Fortunately, this error is not very common and affects only a few rows (between 3 and 5 rows affected).

Even carrying out an exhaustive analysis of the data, it may happen that we do not detect certain problems until we carry out tests with the code. During the tests we detected a problem related to the data format. In the column **Flow Bytes/s** (we can see the list of columns in the table 2), an error occurs because the data is too large or infinite. Therefore, this column must be taken into consideration when cleaning and transforming the data.

Finally, it is convenient to know the format of each of the columns of the dataset, as this information will be necessary when transforming the data, a step described in . It is important to identify what type of characteristics make up our dataset since depending on the type of the characteristic, the algorithms that we use and the way to interpret the data will vary.

We can have the following types of characteristics or variables:

1. **Categorical characteristic:** indicate membership in one or more categories. They may be:
 - Ordinals: they can be classified according to an order although it does not necessarily have to be numerical.
 - Nominal: not classified by order.
2. **Numeric characteristic:** Describe a quantity that can be measured. They may be:
 - Continuous: it can take any value from a given set of real numbers.
 - Discrete: it can take values from a set of different integers.

In the case of our dataset we have identified the following categorical variables:

- Flow ID
- Src IP

- Dst IP
- Src Port
- Dst Port
- Protocol

All the cited variables are nominal categorical characteristics. While the rest of the dataset characteristics are numeric. We must also consider the Label variable, used to perform the labeling. This variable will take an integer value depending on the type of traffic to which the labeled flow belongs, that is, the Label variable is categorical because it indicates the class of traffic to which the flow belongs. This characteristic being our output or objective variable. This is why our goal is to apply supervised machine learning to classify flows, as classification is usually applied when the target variable is qualitative.

Cleaning the dataset

In this section we are going to describe the cleaning that has been carried out on the dataset with which we have worked. Through the detailed analysis in the previous section we have obtained information about the values and fields of the dataset that are susceptible to producing problems. Once the problematic data is known, the next step will be to decide how to treat it. In general, the most common ways of treating data are the following:

- **Delete the value:** useful when the values we want to treat are in small quantity.
- **Leave the value unchanged:** this strategy can be adopted when faced with negative values. We will assume that some algorithms and techniques will not be able to work with these values and, therefore, we will only use those that process negative values.
- **Replace the value:** assume the value that the field will have, that is, replace the problematic value with another value that maintains stability in the data. It is usually used when there are many problem values and the distribution of these is normal. A common strategy is to calculate the mean of the column where the values occur and assign that mean as a new value in the corresponding fields.

In our dataset we have used the following strategies to clean the dataset and avoid detected errors:

- We remove the rows that have been affected by the CICFlowMeter error described in .
- We replace the NaN values by 0
- We eliminate the Flow Bytes/s column, because we have not been able to limit the error that affects it.
- We keep negative values.
- We keep the columns that have all their values at 0. These columns correspond to the information of the *Flags*, which by themselves may not provide relevant information, but may be important when viewed together.

Data transformation

It is very common, when working with large data sets, to find some characteristics represented by means of text strings or other complex data types. The algorithms with which we will work will have problems when processing this type of data. Therefore, a really important step when preparing the data is to convert it to a type of data that is suitable for applying the algorithms. These problematic features can be easily and manually located by looking at the dataset. If we have previously carried out an analysis of characteristics, to know if they are categorical or numerical, this task may be easier.

In the case of the dataset type we are working with, the one generated by CICFlowMeter, we can distinguish the following characteristics that have a problematic data type:

- **Flow ID:** is a text string that uniquely identifies the flow. It has the format: **SourceIP-DestinationIP-SourcePort-DestinationPort-Protocol**
- **Src IP:** is a text string indicating the source IP address.
- **Dst IP:** is a text string indicating the destination IP address.
- **Timestamp:** is a *date* type that represents the time stamp of the stream. It has the format: **dd/mm/aaaa hh:mm:ss AM/PM**

Once these characteristics have been identified, we can decide how we will carry out the conversion and to what format. The rest of the data in our dataset is represented with *floats* and integers, therefore, we will convert the characteristics previously described to this format.

The **Flow ID** field represents an identifier that allows you to locate a specific flow within the data set. Since the only stage in which we need to identify a flow is the labeling phase and since we carry out this identification using a more complete footprint, this field will not be necessary and therefore we can simply remove it.

The **Timestamp** field is of type date. The conversion of this type of data is simple since there are multiple libraries that allow obtaining a numerical representation from a date. The **pandas** library incorporates a function called *timestamp ()* that allows us to convert the given date to **POSIX** or **UNIX** format, that is, the date is defined as the amount of seconds since midnight UTC on **January 1, 1970**.

Finally we must deal with the fields related to the IP addresses. In the dataset we are working with, as well as in most of the datasets that work with data obtained through network traffic, we find two fields with IP addresses: Src IP and Dst IP. We will treat both fields in the same way. Our goal is to obtain a numerical representation of the IP. For this we will carry out a conversion by going through each of the IPs and operating on it in the following way:

Given the IP = C1.C2.C3.C4, we obtain its numerical representation through the equation (.1):

$$newIP = C1 \times 256^3 + C2 \times 256^2 \times C3 \times 256^1 + C4 \times 256^0 \quad (.1)$$

To carry out each of the transformations described in this section, a code has been implemented in **Python** that allows going through the IPs and timestamps to modify them and assign them the new numerical value.

Data preprocessing

Once the possible errors have been removed from the dataset and the data types have been transformed appropriately, the dataset is ready to feed the algorithms that we want to apply. However, it is a good practice to convert all data in the dataset to the same data type and keep it in a suitable equal range of values. The process to accomplish this is called preprocessing. The objective of this phase is to represent the dataset values by means of different values, but that facilitate their processing by the algorithms that will be applied later.

In our case, we have chosen to scale the data, so we have implemented two different methods to perform this task:

- **Normalization:** Scales the input vectors to the unit norm.
- **Standardization:** scales the input vectors to the variance of the unit eliminating the mean.

There are other data preprocessing methods that could be implemented in the future such as: *centering* or *binarization*, however, as a first approach, it has been chosen to include only the two methods already mentioned.

It should be noted that using one method or another can have a significant influence on the results, and the choice of the processing method to use is closely linked to the type of data with which you are working in the dataset, so that some methods offer better results when applied on one data type than on others.

Feature reduction

The feature reduction phase is also optional, since we can train the models with the complete dataset, however, this phase allows to increase the performance of the classification. The objective of this phase is to reduce the number of variables, so that only the characteristics that have the most weight or provide the most information are selected. In other words, it consists of reducing the columns of the dataset to avoid working with irrelevant information.

It is possible to carry out the reduction of characteristics of a data set through several methods [4][5]. In our case we have opted for the "*Univariate feature selection*" method. This technique is based on statistical tests and consists of selecting the best characteristics, these being the ones most closely related to the target variable.

Within the described method there are different algorithms. In our case we have implemented the selection of the best k variables ("**SelectKBest**"). This method selects the characteristics through a scoring function. Through the *scikit-learn* library, you can use the `selectKbest()` method with different scoring functions.

Other methods that have been considered for its implementation are: *low variance*, *Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE)* or *Pearson correlation*.

Dimensionality reduction

The dimensionality reduction stage, like the feature reduction stage, is an optional stage. Reducing the dimensionality of the dataset consists of reducing the data it contains so that we obtain a matrix with smaller dimensions than the original, but whose representation is the same.

This phase has not been implemented in our project at the moment.

Model training

Training the model requires that we distinguish between two data sets. The set that we will call X_{train} that consists of the dataset with which we are going to work but without the data corresponding to the target variable, that is, in our case X_{train} corresponds to the complete dataset except for the *Label* column. On the other hand, we have the set that we will call y_{train} that will be formed by the target variable (the *Label* column in our case).

By using the scikit-learn library and the two data sets mentioned in this section we can create the classifiers that we will use. In our case we have worked with the following algorithms:

- Decision_Tree_Classifier
- Linear_Discriminant_Analysis
- Logistic_Regression_Classifier
- Random_Forest_Classifier
- SGD_Classifier
- GaussianNB_Classifier
- KNeighbors_Classifier
- Quadratic_Discriminant_Analysis
- Ada_Boost_Classifier
- One_Vs_Rest_Classifier
- Mini_Batch_KMeans_Classifier

Model evaluation

Once the model is trained, we can proceed to the evaluation stage. This phase of the process consists of supplying sets of test data, to check the behavior of the model with respect to said data and to verify if the predictions it makes are more correct or less.

In the same way as in the previous section we had to distinguish two sets (X_{train} and y_{train}), to perform the model evaluation we will use the sets X_{test} and y_{test} .

When we carry out the evaluation of the model we will obtain several metrics that allow us to get an idea of the behavior of the corresponding model. These metrics can consist of the precision or *accuracy*, the confusion matrix, and the overtraining or *overfitting*. In the following sections we will see each of these aspects in more detail.

Before going into the details of the metrics, we must make it clear what values are used to calculate these metrics. At this point the concepts of positives and negatives take importance:

- True Positive (TP): positive classified as positive.
- True Negative (TN): negative classified as negative.
- False Positive (FP): negative classified as positive.
- False Negative (FN): positive classified as negative.

The tests carried out followed the following structure:

- Three classification models were used: **Random Forest (RF)**, **Decision Tree (DT)** y **Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)**
- The models were trained using the dataset created on November 27 and 28
- The tests were carried out on the trained models using the dataset generated on October 15 (focused on DoS attacks)

The results obtained, both precision and confusion matrix, are presented in the following sections.

Accuracy measurement

Precision is the metric that indicates how accurate a model is. That is, it is a value that is calculated from the number of classifications that have been carried out correctly and the number of classifications that have been carried out incorrectly. The precision or *accuracy* can be calculated through the equation (.2):

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (.2)$$

The *accuracy* obtained for the RF, DT and LDA models is 0.977474, 0.969946 and 0.963452 respectively. The reports generated by the tool are shown in the figures 4, 5 y 6.

```
Classification report:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

   0       0.97       0.92       0.95     52171
   1       0.98       0.99       0.99     193586

 micro avg       0.98       0.98       0.98    245757
 macro avg       0.97       0.96       0.97    245757
weighted avg       0.98       0.98       0.98    245757
```

Figure 4: Random Forest Report

```

Classification report:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

   0:   0.93      0.93      0.93     52171
   1:   0.98      0.98      0.98    193586

 micro avg   0.97      0.97      0.97    245757
 macro avg   0.95      0.96      0.96    245757
weighted avg   0.97      0.97      0.97    245757

```

Figure 5: Decision Tree Report

```

Classification report:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

   0:   0.99      0.83      0.91     52171
   1:   0.96      1.00      0.98    193586

 micro avg   0.96      0.96      0.96    245757
 macro avg   0.97      0.92      0.94    245757
weighted avg   0.96      0.96      0.96    245757

```

Figure 6: LDA Report

Confusion matrix

We can represent the predictions generated by the model through a confusion matrix. This matrix allows us to quickly and clearly observe the number of correct and incorrect predictions. In the images we can see the corresponding confusion matrices for the classification models with which the tests have been carried out.

Figure 7: Random Forest Matrix

Figure 8: Decision Tree Matrix

Figure 9: LDA Matrix

Overfitting and underfitting measurement

The problems known as overfitting and underfitting [6] correspond to an erroneous generalization of the machine. When we train a classifier, we do it with the objective of later supplying it with data so that it can assign a class to it based on the data with which it has been trained. If the amount of data is not adequate, two effects can occur.

- **Overfitting:** if the data that we have supplied of a certain class is too much then it may happen that the generalization made by the model is too restrictive and generates false negatives.
- **Underfitting:** if the data we have supplied is very scarce, the machine will not be able to distinguish between cases very precisely and false positives will be generated.

We can analyze our case, as it is very susceptible to presenting some of these problems. For the first tests we carried out, we only used traffic that comes from DoS attacks carried out with the Hulk tool.

In several of the models tested, our tool has a high precision or *accuracy* when detecting this type of traffic, however, it is very likely that when using another DoS attack generation tool, our model will not generalize OK, and don't tag some of this new traffic as an attack, this effect is what we call **overfitting**. On the other hand, the test model has been trained and tested with two datasets of 100,000 records each, distributed in such a way that 50,000 records correspond to traffic labeled as normal and the other 50,000 correspond to traffic labeled as attack. The size of the datasets used for the tests, therefore, is not very large and this can cause the model to present **underfitting**, that is, it is not sufficiently restrictive when classifying the traffic.

To know the proportion of **overfitting** or **underfitting** that the built models present, we have included in our code a function from the *scikit-learn* library that allows us to generate graphs of curves. This function is known as **learning curves** and the graph generated by it presents two curves, one corresponding to the test model and the other corresponding to the training model so that we can see if the model is generalizing in a very restrictive or very little restrictive.

TOOL VALIDATION

To carry out the validation of the tool, a replica of a study already carried out previously has been carried out. After the development process, it is necessary to put the tool to the test to know for sure if it can be used in a real traffic analysis project. In the case of this project, development and testing have been focused on the dataset format (*dataset*) provided by the **CICFlowMeter** tool instead of **NetFlow**. For this reason, a search has been made for data sets that have been constructed in the aforementioned format. The literature review has revealed a list of candidate data sets for the aforementioned experiment. Among the *datasets* mentioned, you can find the one called **CIC-IDS-2017**. This *dataset* has been generated using the **CICFlowMeter** tool. Once the data set to be used has been detected, studies have been sought that work on said data set, but this time without taking into account the restriction of public access that was used during the literature review. Finally, the study selected is the one presented in the article [1]¹. This study focuses on optimizing the *dataset* mentioned above. Before delving into the study carried out, it is important to mention the content of the *dataset* **CIC-IDS-2017**. This dataset has several files that focus on different attacks:

- *Friday-WorkingHours-Afternoon-DDos.pcap_ISCX*
- *Friday-WorkingHours-Afternoon-PortScan.pcap_ISCX*
- *Friday-WorkingHours-Morning.pcap_ISCX*
- *Thursday-WorkingHours-Afternoon-Infiltration.pcap_ISCX*
- *Thursday-WorkingHours-Morning-WebAttacks.pcap_ISCX*

The validation of the tool has focused solely on the data set that addresses port scanning because it is one of the most common attacks on the APTs problem, as seen in the initial chapter of this memory. On the other hand, the study carried out in the reference article consists of the optimization of each of the *datasets* listed above, for this the following steps are carried out:

1. **Cleaning the dataset:** elimination of redundant characteristics, elimination of characteristics that do not add value, substitution of NaN values for zero and substitution of infinite values for the mean of the records of the corresponding characteristic .
2. **Reduction of the characteristics by calculating their variance.** Any characteristic with variance of zero is eliminated.
3. **Feature reduction using PCA.**

After applying the previous steps to the *dataset* corresponding to the port scan traffic, the researchers reduce the characteristics of the same to 23 characteristics (of the initial 84). After optimizing the data set, the researchers apply three classification algorithms: **KNN**, **Naïve Bayes** and **C4.5** (decision tree). For the validation process carried out in this project, all the steps presented in the study have been carried out with the exception of the reduction of characteristics using **PCA**. Instead, the *selectKBest* method has been used (to obtain the same number of characteristics as those used in the aforementioned study, that is, 23 characteristics) from the **Scikit-learn** library because This method is the one that was decided to implement in the tool during the design phase. The results obtained are shown in the table 6:

¹The aforementioned article has been provided by the authors.

Table 6: Results obtained in the reference article vs. results obtained through the developed tool

Algorithm	Accuracy Reference	Accuracy of the experiment
KNN	99.9%	99.96%
C4.5	99.9%	99.9%
Naïve Bayes	98%	70.0%

In the external study, the hyperparameters used when training the models were not provided, therefore, for the experiment carried out, the default parameters of the **Scikit-learn** algorithms were used. As can be seen, the results obtained are satisfactory, having obtained the same results for the models **KNN** and **C4.5**, the lowest *accuracy* obtained in this work being the one corresponding to the Naïve Bayes model. The results obtained for this last model are far from those obtained in the reference study, however, this difference is attributed to the use, in this experiment, of the default parameters and the use of a different method for the selection process of characteristics.

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